

THE SITUATIONAL NOMINATIONS AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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This thesis statement examines the history of the nomination process tracing from situational nomination to exploring theories, examples, and characteristics of it.

It is no coincidence that classical linguistics of the 19th - early 20th centuries, considering cognition as a frozen category and language as a static formation, for decades saw the connection between language and thinking in the “word-concept” relationship.

The materialistic definition of language as a social phenomenon, the most important means of communication, and the immediate reality of thought oblige the linguist to take into account and study not only dynamics and dialectics of human cognition and language but also turn to historical materialism, which reveals the specific conditions and forms of material production and cultural-historical experience, reflected in the originality of the nomenclature of lexical units and in the difference in the characteristics by which the name is derived. An adequate study of the nominative aspect of language requires, first of all, the study of its content, and the relationship of language with thinking and reality.

An “untouched” but worthy of attention nominative facts include the so-called situational nominations. According to V.G. Gak, they are contrasted with elemental ones as denoting not an object of reality, but a certain micro-situation. It seems that the situational nomination is an integral component of nominative activity, and turning to this type of nomination will significantly enrich our understanding of the mechanisms of verbalization of human knowledge, which is not limited only to comprehending the specifics of objects of reality in their statics, but also evaluates and characterizes their relationships and actions with them.

Situational nomination, as defined by V.G. Gak, “as a nominee has a micro-situation, i.e. an event, a fact that combines a number of elements. As can be seen from this definition, for the researcher the terms event and situational nomination act as equivalent, i.e. V.G. Gak equates the concepts of “micro-situation” and “event”. The following types of situational nominations were determined:

1. Nominations of the macro-situation by indicating its impact on the recipient: fun, sadness - graduation after 11th grade; flattened, sad, bored - the last City Day; embarrassment, eclipse, inspiration - first date; confidence, hope, interesting, delight – the last presidential elections.
2. Evaluation nominations. The presented nominations express the overall rating: fairy tale, super, fun, relaxation - graduation after 11th grade; deserved, shame, well done, victory – Samuel’s second place at Eurovision; it came true, success, luck, freebie - getting an apartment.
3. Nominations through its components. In this situational nomination model, the proposed macro-situation is designated through metonymic transfer (part of the whole): by any element of the event or by the place where it took place: questionnaire, personality, me - school event; “pumpkin, witch, horror films – Halloween; equations, logic, knowledge, ingenuity – competition; balls, flower garden, crowd, heat, traffic - City Day.
4. Nominations through the attitude of the nominator to her existence. The model is characterized by a number of antinomies: 1) the nominator denies the proposed event the status of an event - the nominator thinks of it precisely as an event. For example, for one part of the employee respondents, the last presidential election, getting an apartment is an event (that’s what they called them), and for the other – a non-event (characteristic nominations: routine, habit). 2) The nominator refers to the event as an inevitable, natural phenomenon - the event was unexpected for the nominator: inevitability, fate - a wedding; inevitability-economic crisis; duty – presidential elections; surprise - first date; regularity; expected; self-reliance.

5. Nominations of the macro-situation through its consequence, result: collapse, collapse - economic crisis; student, study, continuation - admission to university; death – COVID-19.
6. Hyper-hyponymous nominations: holiday – Halloween; celebration - wedding; mobilization – purchasing a cell phone; sport –football.
7. Nominations of the macro-situation through its cause: negligence; gift, purchase.

Within the above classification, all types can be combined into two groups: 1) nominations that reflect the connection of the nominee with the person; and 2) nominations associated with the nominee's own characteristics. Latest nominations groups are also quite subjective, since the choice of an object's attribute as a nominative one is determined by the nominator, but they are more focused on reflecting the real peculiarities of the named phenomenon [1].

In quantitative terms, the first group is represented by a large number of nominative units: these are emotionally evaluative nominations, including those conveying the assessment metaphorically, and names that reflect the influence of the macro-situation on the nominator. This is due to the nature of the nomination: events that took place in the lives of the respondents themselves were proposed for designation - in some, they were direct participants (for example, all school events, graduation, first date, etc.). Events that have occurred in a person's life, as a rule, are stored in his mind in the form of a set of episodes, details, and other persons, supplemented by a general impression (general assessment). The identified types of nominations show that, naming this holistic phenomenon, a person can go in different ways: choose one of the components of the event as a nominative feature, fit it into a number of other, similar or adjacent phenomena, or express the general impression of the event in a nomination. As the experimental data showed, the general impression of an event lies on the surface of a person's consciousness and is easiest to reproduce, especially if the situation itself is connected with a person and involves a vivid emotional response [2].

The list of used literature

1. Гак В.Г. К типологии лингвистических номинаций // Языковая номинация: Общие вопросы. – М., 1977.
2. Гак В.Г. [Языковые преобразования](#) 2000.

